

Neuroquery Validation

```
In [1]: pip install -q neuroquery
```

Note: you may need to restart the kernel to use updated packages.

```
In [2]: from neuroquery import fetch_neuroquery_model, NeuroQueryModel
from nilearn.plotting import view_img

import numpy as np
```

Load neuroquery encoder

```
In [3]: encoder = NeuroQueryModel.from_data_dir(fetch_neuroquery_model())
vocab = np.array(encoder.full_vocabulary())
```

Helper methods for accessing neuroquery API

```
In [4]: def find_query_terms(query):
result = encoder(query)
query_tfidf = result['raw_tfidf'].toarray().astype(bool)[0]
return vocab[query_tfidf].tolist()

def find_similar_documents(query, limit=10):
result = encoder(query)
return result['similar_documents']

def vectorizer_transform(query):
return vocab[encoder.vectorizer.transform([query]).toarray().astype
```

What is neuroquery identifying in these terms?

```
In [5]: find_query_terms("Children with ASD")
```

```
/Users/andretelfer/miniconda3/lib/python3.12/site-packages/neuroquery/i
mg_utils.py:21: UserWarning: Data array used to create a new image cont
ains 64-bit ints. This is likely due to creating the array with numpy a
nd passing `int` as the `dtype`. Many tools such as FSL and SPM cannot
deal with int64 in Nifti images, so for compatibility the data has been
converted to int32.
```

```
masker = maskers.NiftiMasker(mask_img=mask_img).fit()
```

```
Out[5]: ['asd', 'children']
```

```
In [6]: find_query_terms("Children without ASD")
```

```
Out[6]: ['asd', 'children', 'without']
```

Encode documents

```
In [7]: # Number of papers shown on neuroquery
n_papers = 30
```

```
In [8]: doc1 = find_similar_documents("Children with ASD").head(n_papers)
doc1
```

Out [8]:

	pmid	title	pubmed_url	sim
0	17707658	Atypical neural substrates of Embedded Figures...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17707658	0.8
1	24497750	Atypical Neural Processing of Ironic and Since...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24497750	0.7
2	21078973	Neural signatures of autism	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21078973	0.70
3	26261885	Atypical spatiotemporal signatures of working ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26261885	0.68
4	28193532	Age-dependent atypicalities in body- and face-...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28193532	0.67
5	26788282	The effect of gender on the neuroanatomy of ch...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26788282	0.66
6	28869842	Changes in intrinsic local connectivity after ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28869842	0.66
7	20656041	fMRI evidence of neural abnormalities in the s...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20656041	0.66
8	16481375	Neural basis of irony comprehension in childre...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16481375	0.66
9	24297883	Oxytocin enhances brain function in children w...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24297883	0.66
10	24294201	Reduced Theta Connectivity during Set-Shifting...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24294201	0.66
11	19683584	Investigating the predictive value of whole-br...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19683584	0.58
12	26454817	Insula response and connectivity during social...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26454817	0.58
13	19068486	Functional Connectivity of the Inferior Fronta...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19068486	0.56

14	25552572	Neural and cortisol responses during play with...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25552572	0.56
15	26329119	Reduced cortical thickness and its association...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26329119	0.56
16	24636205	Neural bases of Theory of Mind in children wit...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24636205	0.56
17	25533997	Inverse fluoxetine effects on inhibitory brain...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25533997	0.56
18	20153764	Coherent motion processing in autism spectrum ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20153764	0.56
19	28867997	Autism Spectrum Disorder Related Functional Co...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28867997	0.56
20	27081401	A functional neuroimaging study of fusiform re...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27081401	0.56
21	22859975	Gamma Activation in Young People with Autism S...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/22859975	0.56
22	24016745	Equivalent neural responses in children and ad...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24016745	0.56
23	23954299	Brain Organization Underlying Superior Mathema...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23954299	0.56
24	21998649	Autism Spectrum Disorders and Schizophrenia: M...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21998649	0.56
25	23768913	Differences in global and local level informat...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23768913	0.56

Atypical modulation of

26	23986678	distant functional conn...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23986678	0.5
27	25057329	The neural correlates of visuo-spatial working...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25057329	0.5
28	18958161	Neural Basis of Self and Other Representation ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18958161	0.5
29	23784073	Age-dependent changes in the neural substrates...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23784073	0.5

```
In [9]: doc2 = find_similar_documents("Children without ASD").head(n_papers)
doc2
```

Out [9]:

	pmid	title	pubmed_url	sim
0	17707658	Atypical neural substrates of Embedded Figures...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17707658	0.8
1	24497750	Atypical Neural Processing of Ironic and Since...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24497750	0.7
2	21078973	Neural signatures of autism	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21078973	0.6
3	26261885	Atypical spatiotemporal signatures of working ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26261885	0.6
4	26788282	The effect of gender on the neuroanatomy of ch...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26788282	0.6
5	28193532	Age-dependent atypicalities in body- and face-...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28193532	0.6
6	28869842	Changes in intrinsic local connectivity after ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28869842	0.6
7	20656041	fMRI evidence of neural abnormalities in the s...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20656041	0.6
8	16481375	Neural basis of irony comprehension in childre...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16481375	0.6

9	24297883	Oxytocin enhances brain function in children w...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24297883	0.5
10	24294201	Reduced Theta Connectivity during Set-Shifting...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24294201	0.5
11	24016745	Equivalent neural responses in children and ad...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24016745	0.5
12	19683584	Investigating the predictive value of whole-br...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19683584	0.5
13	26329119	Reduced cortical thickness and its association...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26329119	0.5
14	19068486	Functional Connectivity of the Inferior Fronta...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19068486	0.5
15	26454817	Insula response and connectivity during social...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26454817	0.5
16	25552572	Neural and cortisol responses during play with...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25552572	0.5
17	24636205	Neural bases of Theory of Mind in children wit...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24636205	0.5
18	25533997	Inverse fluoxetine effects on inhibitory brain...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25533997	0.5
19	20153764	Coherent motion processing in autism spectrum ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20153764	0.5
20	28867997	Autism Spectrum Disorder Related Functional Co...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28867997	0.5
21	27081401	A functional neuroimaging study of fusiform re...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27081401	0.5

22	22859975	Gamma Activation in Young People with Autism S...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/22859975	0.5
23	23954299	Brain Organization Underlying Superior Mathema...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23954299	0.5
24	21998649	Autism Spectrum Disorders and Schizophrenia: M...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21998649	0.5
25	23768913	Differences in global and local level informat...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23768913	0.5
26	23986678	Atypical modulation of distant functional conn...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23986678	0.5
27	25057329	The neural correlates of visuo-spatial working...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25057329	0.5
28	18958161	Neural Basis of Self and Other Representation ...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18958161	0.5
29	21743819	Enhanced Neural Responses to Rule Violation in...	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21743819	0.5

```
In [10]: terms1 = [vectorizer_transform(x) for x in doc1.title.tolist()]
terms2 = [vectorizer_transform(x) for x in doc2.title.tolist()]
```

```
# Show an example paper
print("Example", f'"{doc1.title[0]}"', '\n->', terms1[0])
```

Example "Atypical neural substrates of Embedded Figures Task performance in children with Autism Spectrum Disorders"
-> ['atypical', 'autism spectrum disorder', 'children', 'neural', 'performance', 'task']

Compute Shannon Entropy

```
In [11]: from collections import Counter

def flatten(tokens_list):
    return [token for title in tokens_list for token in title]

def token_probabilities(tokens):
    counts = Counter(tokens)
    total = sum(counts.values())
    probs = np.array([count / total for count in counts.values()])
    return probs
```

```

return probs

def shannon_entropy(tokens_list):
    tokens = flatten(tokens_list)
    probs = token_probabilities(tokens)
    return -np.sum(probs * np.log2(probs))

entropy_group1 = shannon_entropy(terms1)
entropy_group2 = shannon_entropy(terms2)

print("Group 1 entropy:", entropy_group1)
print("Group 2 entropy:", entropy_group2)

```

Group 1 entropy: 5.982174915814449
Group 2 entropy: 5.977596230038838

Jaccard Overlap

```

In [12]: s1 = set(flatten(terms1))
s2 = set(flatten(terms2))

len(s1 & s2) / len(s1 | s2) # Jaccard overlap

```

Out[12]: 0.9711538461538461

Leakage of ASD markers

'autism' or 'asd' mentioned in every title

```

In [13]: np.mean([any('autism' in w or 'asd' in w for w in d) for d in terms1])

```

Out[13]: np.float64(1.0)

```

In [14]: np.mean([any('autism' in w or 'asd' in w for w in d) for d in terms2])

```

Out[14]: np.float64(1.0)

Z-Test on ASD markers

No point computing, both have 100% presence of 'asd' and 'autism' markers

TF-IDF Centroids/Cosine difference between groups

```

In [15]: from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_distances

from random import shuffle

def identity_tokenizer(doc):
    return doc

# Combine all documents
all_docs = terms1 + terms2

vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(lowercase=False, tokenizer=identity_tokenizer)
X = vectorizer.fit_transform(all_docs)

# Split back into groups

```

```

n1 = len(terms1)
X1 = X[:n1]
X2 = X[n1:]

# Compute centroids
centroid1 = X1.mean(axis=0)
centroid2 = X2.mean(axis=0)

# Cosine distance
distance = cosine_distances(centroid1.A, centroid2.A)[0,0]
print("Cosine distance between groups:", distance)

# Permutation test
n_permutations = 1000
perm_distances = []

labels = [0]*n1 + [1]*len(terms2)
for _ in range(n_permutations):
    shuffle(labels)
    idx1 = [i for i, l in enumerate(labels) if l == 0]
    idx2 = [i for i, l in enumerate(labels) if l == 1]

    centroid1_perm = X[idx1].mean(axis=0)
    centroid2_perm = X[idx2].mean(axis=0)

    perm_distance = cosine_distances(centroid1_perm.A, centroid2_perm.A)
    perm_distances.append(perm_distance)

p_value = np.mean([d >= distance for d in perm_distances])
print("Permutation test p-value:", p_value)

```

Cosine distance between groups: 0.010134467535123592

```

/Users/andretelfer/miniconda3/lib/python3.12/site-packages/sklearn/feature_extraction/text.py:517: UserWarning: The parameter 'token_pattern' will not be used since 'tokenizer' is not None'
  warnings.warn(

```

Permutation test p-value: 1.0

KL Divergence

```

In [16]: from scipy.stats import entropy

def flatten(tokens_list):
    return [token for doc in tokens_list for token in doc]

tokens1 = flatten(terms1)
tokens2 = flatten(terms2)

# Count frequencies
count1 = Counter(tokens1)
count2 = Counter(tokens2)

# Build union of all tokens
all_tokens = set(count1.keys()) | set(count2.keys())

# Convert counts to probability vectors
alpha = 1e-6 # smoothing
p1 = np.array([count1.get(tok,0)+alpha for tok in all_tokens])
p2 = np.array([count2.get(tok,0)+alpha for tok in all_tokens])
p1 /= p1.sum()
p2 /= p2.sum()

# KL divergence (directional)

```

```
kl_1_2 = entropy(p1, p2) #  $D(P || Q)$   
kl_2_1 = entropy(p2, p1) #  $D(Q || P)$   
  
print("KL(P|Q):", kl_1_2)  
print("KL(Q|P):", kl_2_1)
```

KL(P|Q): 0.0802200814953589

KL(Q|P): 0.13847444189207436